

Development of Agricultural Infrastructure and Material Logistics Support of Farms

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ABSTRACT: The article discusses the prospects for the development of entrepreneurship in agriculture in our country, sustainable economic development of farms, which are its main and leading link.

KEY WORDS: agriculture, agribusiness, farming, sustainable development, land, water, resources, infrastructure, prospects.

INTRODUCTION: In connection with the transition to a market economy, radical reforms have been carried out in the organizational structure of agriculture in the country. First of all, measures have been taken to reorganize state and collective farms, in a short time they were replaced by farms based on the principles of labour and property interests. At the same time, special attention was paid to the development of farmers and farms, which are a new form of management in the agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

A number of global problems caused by recent global climate change have had a direct impact on agricultural production, requires increasing the efficiency of the use of limited resources. In particular, the complex situation created by today's coronavirus pandemic requires the need for more sustainable development of farms. This is due to the fact that a significant part of the population's needs for food, industry and raw materials are grown by farms. In this regard, the study of the factors influencing the sustainable development of farms on the basis of today's requirements and their rational use has become a topical issue. Our country has created a fairly solid resource base, legal, organizational, economic and institutional base to ensure sustainable development of farms. In the agricultural sector, it is possible to achieve sustainability, primarily through the use of efficient methods of land and water resources. Priority development of farms as the most effective form of organization of this process, the formation of a reliable system and mechanisms for material logistics and financing in accordance with the principles of a market economy is an important factor in ensuring the sustainable development of farms.

ANALYSIS OF RELEVANT REFERENCES: Formation of farms, objective necessity, factors, stages and ideas of continuous development, theoretical and methodological foundations from foreign scientists. E.Kasl, M.Beker, J.Pretty, P.C.Kesavan, M.S.Swaminathan, R.Costanza, C.B.Flora, R.A.Cramb, C.Leeuwis, N.P.Makarov, A.A.Nikitina, S.G.Khanmagamedov, A.A.Anfinogrnova, N.A.Yakovenko, I.G.Ushachev, A.G.Paptsov, N.K.Dolgushkin, A.F.Serkov, V.V.Maslova, V.S.Chekalin and reflected in the studies of others.

From our local scientists on scientific and practical issues of reforming agribusiness and the formation and development of farms in Uzbekistan. A.M.Jo'rayev, Ch.Murodov, T.Sh.Shodiyev, U.A.Saydahmedov, U.A.Nazarova, T.H.Farmonov, U.V.Gafurov, A.A.Rajapov, F.T.Egamberdiyev, U.P.Umurzoqov and others have done thorough research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: In the above study, to identify the factors influencing the sustainable development of farms, which are the leading link in agriculture, study of foreign experience in sustainable economic development of farms, analysis of the socio-economic consequences of economic development of farms and the impact on environmental balance, determination and scientific substantiation of the main directions of sustainable economic development of farms, it is expedient to develop ways of using organizational-economic and legal mechanisms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS: As of January 1, 2020, the number of farms was 92.6 thousand, farms 5 million, The number of organizations engaged in agricultural activities amounted to 27.6 thousand.

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The volume of agricultural production in 2019 will reach 215.7 trillion. soum or 102.7% over the corresponding period of 2018, including agricultural products - 108.3 trillion. soum (103,7%), livestock products - 107.4 trillion. soums (101.7%). At the end of 2019, the share of farms in the structure of agricultural production was higher than that of other categories of farms (Table 1).

Table 1 economic indicator of farms for the production of agricultural products

Indicators	2010 year	2015 year	2016 year	2017 year	2018 year	2019 year
Agriculture, billion soums	5038,9	10266	12013,5	16271	27982,5	34724,7
Livestock, bln. soums	3615,4	5771,6	6178,1	7313,5	26226,4	28287,6
Arable land, thousand ha	5290,9	5248,8	5351,3	5384,0	6247,3	6256,9

Source: The state committee of the republic of Uzbekistan on statistics

According to the table, in 2010 farms spent 5038.9 billion soums on agriculture and livestock produced goods worth 3615.4 billion soums, at that time, farms owned 5,290.9 thousand hectares of land. By 2019, the volume of agricultural production will reach 34,724.7 billion soums, and livestock. Equal to 28287.6 billion in UZS, Compared to 2010, it increased by 6.9 and 7.8 times, respectively. It is reasonable to assume that this is primarily due to an increase in the population's ability to pay and an improvement in the standard of living. The sown area in 2005 was 5290.9 thousand hectares by 2019, due to the development of new lands, this figure increased by 18.3% to 6,256.9 thousand hectares.

In recent years, the growth rate of agricultural production in the Namangan region has been maintained at about 3% per year. However, this is not enough for a region where natural and climatic conditions are favourable for agriculture, and 83.2% of agricultural land is irrigated.

Of course, sustainable economic growth of farms is closely related to a number of factors. In particular, the product uses the services of various categories of enterprises and organizations in the production, processing and sale. Most provide machinery, fertilizers, fuel, money and similar resources, while others buy agricultural products for processing and provide social services. Infrastructure institutions are organizations that bring together and support a given category of enterprises in a single market. The main functions of rural infrastructure are as follows, as can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Basic functions of rural infrastructure

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The use of market infrastructure services by farms, firstly, will help them receive more income from their activities and, ultimately, contribute to the state budget, and secondly, workers laid off as a result of corporate farm reform will also be provided workplaces. The use of market infrastructure services by farms, firstly, will help them receive more income from their activities and, ultimately, contribute to the state budget, and secondly, workers laid off as a result of corporate farm reform will also be provided workplaces. These organizations include: retail outlets for the sale of agricultural products, transport service providers, manufacturers of containers for the transport of agricultural products, veterinary service points. They cannot operate at a level that fully meets the demand.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop the material and logistic base of each farm based on its capabilities. In our opinion, the main directions for the development of farm material logistics are as follows (Figure 2):

Figure 2: The main directions of development of material logistics support of farms.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS: Based on the foregoing:

Creating an economically viable integrated mechanization system suitable for each agricultural zone, and strengthening the material logistics base of service enterprises through the widespread use of production automation tools;

Correct management of the use of fertilizers in agricultural production and approach to economically viable biological agents, as well as the use of advanced irrigation technologies to improve land reclamation and achieve complete water supply for agriculture;

Expansion of processing enterprises that meet the requirements of a market economy, based on existing opportunities in the region, thereby accelerating the construction of industrial buildings and structures on a large scale, improving construction;

Further expansion of financial services, including preferential leasing, lending, accelerating the work of information and consulting centres;

Wider introduction into practice of new techniques and technologies, including the use of mini-technologies, methods of effective use of artificial irrigation techniques;

It is necessary to increase the level of provision and electrification of livestock farms with productive breeds of animals, as well as the creation and production of mass, rapidly maturing varieties of seeds that can withstand diseases of agricultural crops.

The correct organization of the measures taken, the transfer of land to responsible farmers, who will become the real owners, will ultimately serve to further increase agricultural production and improve the standard of living of our people.

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